

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

2026, №6 (26)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

Научный журнал по фундаментальным
и клиническим проблемам медицины,
основанный в 2022 году Бухарским государственным
медицинским институтом имени Абу Али ибн Сино.
Периодичность издания - один раз в месяц.

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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2026, № 6 (26)

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Сайт <https://bsmi.uz/journals/fundamental-ya-klinik-tibbiyot-ahborotnomasi/>

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О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28 мая 2022 года.

Журнал внесен в список
утвержденный приказом № 370/б
от 8 мая 2025 года реестром ВАК
в раздел медицинских наук.

Отпечатано в типографии ООО
“Шарк-Бухоро”. г. Бухара,
ул. Ўзбекистон Мустакиллиги, 70/2.

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE SMALL INTESTINE CAUSED BY DOMESTIC GAS POISONING AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF CHRONIC ALCOHOLISM**Ibodova D.F.**

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Resume. The article analyzes the morphological, morphometric, and immunohistochemical changes occurring in the small intestine of outbred laboratory rats as a result of domestic gas poisoning against the background of chronic alcoholism. The study was conducted on 3-, 9-, and 15-month-old rats, which were divided into control, experimental, and correction groups. Morphological examinations revealed that the combined effects of chronic alcoholism and domestic gas exposure intensified destructive and dystrophic processes in the intestinal mucosa, leading to disruption of villous architecture, deformation of intestinal crypts, and pathological alterations in the microcirculatory bed. Immunohistochemical analysis demonstrated changes in proliferative activity and angiogenesis markers. Following corrective treatment, partial restoration of the structural organization of the intestinal mucosa was observed.

Keywords: chronic alcoholism, domestic gas poisoning, small intestine, morphology, morphometry, immunohistochemistry, rat.

СУРУНКАЛИ АЛКОГОЛИЗМ ФОНИДА МАИШИЙ ГАЗДАН ЗАҲАРЛАНИШ ОҚИБАТИДА ИНГИЧКА ИЧАҚДА ЮЗАГА КЕЛАДИГАН МОРФОЛОГИК ЎЗГАРИШЛАР**Ибодова Д.Ф.**

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Резюме. Мақолада сурункали алкоголизм фонида маиший газ билан заҳарланиш натижасида оқ зотсиз лаборатория каламушлари ингичка ичагида юзага келадиган морфологик, морфометрия ва иммуногистокимёвий ўзгаришлар таҳлил қилинган. Тадқиқот 3, 9 ва 15 ойлик каламушларда ўтказилиб, назорат, тажриба ҳамда коррекция гуруҳлари шакллантирилди. Морфологик текширувлар натижасида сурункали алкоголизм ва маиший газнинг биргаликдаги таъсири ингичка ичак шиллиқ қаватида деструктив-дистрофик жараёнларни кучайтириши, виллуслар архитектоникасининг бузилиши, крипталарнинг деформацияси ҳамда микроциркулятор ўзанда патологик ўзгаришларни юзага келтириши аниқланди. Иммуногистокимёвий текширувлар пролифератив фаоллик ва ангиогенез кўрсаткичларининг ўзгаришини кўрсатди. Коррекциядан сўнг шиллиқ қаватнинг структуравий тикланиши кузатилди.

Калит сўзлар: сурункали алкоголизм, маиший газ, ингичка ичак, морфология, морфометрия, иммуногистокимё, каламуш.

МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ В ТОНКОЙ КИШКЕ ПРИ ОТРАВЛЕНИИ БЫТОВЫМ ГАЗОМ НА ФОНЕ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО АЛКОГОЛИЗМА**Ибодова Д.Ф.**

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Резюме. В статье проанализированы морфологические, морфометрические и иммуногистохимические изменения, возникающие в тонкой кишке белых беспородных лабораторных крыс при отравлении бытовым газом на фоне хронического алкоголизма. Исследование проведено на крысах в возрасте 3, 9 и 15 месяцев, разделённых на контрольную, экспериментальную и коррекционную группы. Результаты морфологического исследования показали, что сочетанное воздействие хронической алкогольной интоксикации и бытового газа усиливает деструктивно-дистрофические процессы в слизистой оболочке тонкой кишки, приводит к нарушению архитектоники ворсинок, деформации кишечных крипт и развитию патологических изменений в микроциркуляторном русле. Иммуногистохимическое исследование выявило изменения показателей пролиферативной активности и ангиогенеза. После проведения коррекции отмечалось частичное восстановление структурной организации слизистой оболочки тонкой кишки.

Ключевые слова: хронический алкоголизм, бытовой газ, тонкая кишка, морфология, морфометрия, иммуногистохимия, крыса.

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Introduction. Chronic alcoholism and domestic gas poisoning remain among the most significant medical and social problems in modern healthcare. According to the World Health Organization, the incidence of alcohol-related diseases and mortality continues to increase annually, leading to structural and functional disorders in numerous organs and systems of the body [13]. Long-term alcohol exposure causes profound morphological alterations in the organs of the digestive system, particularly in the small intestine. These changes are characterized by dystrophic degeneration of intestinal epithelial cells, shortening of intestinal villi, and suppression of regenerative processes [2, 1].

In recent years, considerable attention has been focused on the adverse effects of alcohol on the intestinal barrier function. Studies have demonstrated that alcohol disrupts intercellular junctions between enterocytes, increases intestinal permeability, and contributes to the development of chronic inflammatory processes within the intestinal wall [14, 12]. One of the main pathogenic factors in domestic gas poisoning is carbon monoxide. Carbon monoxide binds strongly to hemoglobin, resulting in tissue hypoxia and impaired oxygen delivery to organs and tissues [4]. Under hypoxic conditions, disturbances in intestinal blood circulation, cellular energy deficiency, and destructive structural changes may develop within the intestinal wall [7].

Several researchers have reported that carbon monoxide intoxication leads to microcirculatory disturbances in the intestine, including vascular stasis, capillary dilation, and perivascular edema [11, 6]. In addition, hypoxic conditions have been shown to reduce the proliferative activity of epithelial cells and limit the regenerative capacity of intestinal tissues [5]. Although chronic alcoholism and carbon monoxide intoxication have been extensively studied separately, the combined effects of these factors on intestinal tissues remain insufficiently investigated [10]. In particular, there is limited information regarding age-related morphological characteristics and the regenerative changes occurring after corrective treatment [9].

Currently, alongside conventional morphological methods, immunohistochemical techniques are widely used in experimental and clinical research. The Ki-67 marker is commonly employed to assess proliferative activity, whereas CD31 serves as an indicator of microcirculatory status and angiogenesis [8]. The application of these markers provides valuable information regarding the severity of pathological alterations and the regenerative potential of affected tissues [3]. Therefore, the investigation of morphological, morphometric, and immunohistochemical changes in the small intestine following domestic gas poisoning against the background of chronic alcoholism represents a relevant scientific and practical issue.

Aim of the study. To investigate the morphological and morphometric characteristics of the small intestine resulting from domestic gas poisoning against the background of chronic alcoholism, as well as the structural changes occurring after corrective treatment.

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted on 3-, 9-, and 15-month-old outbred laboratory rats. The animals were divided into control, experimental, and correction groups.

In the experimental groups, a model of chronic alcoholism was induced, followed by exposure to domestic gas to simulate toxic poisoning. Animals in the correction groups received standard therapeutic and restorative treatment after intoxication. For morphological examination, small intestine specimens were collected and fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin. The tissues subsequently underwent routine histological processing, and paraffin blocks were prepared. Sections 5–7 μm thick were obtained and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and Van Gieson's stain.

Morphometric analysis was performed using digital microscopy. The following parameters were evaluated: villus height; villus width; crypt depth; mucosal thickness; epithelial layer thickness; number of goblet cells; diameter of microcirculatory vessels. Immunohistochemical examinations were carried out using Ki-67 and CD31 markers to assess proliferative activity and angiogenesis.

The obtained data were statistically processed using standard software packages and expressed as mean \pm standard error ($M \pm m$). Differences between groups were evaluated using Student's t-test. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

Results and Discussion. The small intestine of 3-, 9-, and 15-month-old rats in the control groups exhibited a normal layered structure, with the mucosa, submucosa, muscular layer, and serosa clearly distinguishable. Intestinal villi were regularly arranged, the columnar epithelium was well preserved, and the crypts displayed normal morphological characteristics. In the 3-month-old experimental group, destructive alterations were observed at the tips of the villi, accompanied by vacuolar degeneration of epithelial cells and focal desquamation. The microcirculatory bed demonstrated vascular dilation and perivascular edema.

In the 9-month-old experimental group, pathological changes became more pronounced. The villi were shortened and deformed, while disruption of crypt architecture, epithelial cell degeneration, and lymphoplasmacytic infiltration were observed. Focal hemorrhages and necrobiotic lesions were also detected in some areas. The most severe alterations were identified in 15-month-old rats. A marked reduction in the number and height of villi was accompanied by mucosal atrophy. In addition, microcirculatory vessels exhib-

ited signs of stasis and thrombotic changes. These findings indicate that the damaging effects of chronic alcoholism combined with domestic gas intoxication become more pronounced with increasing age.

Morphometric analysis revealed a decrease in villus height and mucosal thickness, alterations in crypt depth, and an increase in the diameter of microcirculatory vessels in all experimental groups. All parameters differed significantly from those of the control groups ($p < 0.05$). Immunohistochemical examination demonstrated a reduction in Ki-67 expression, indicating suppression of regenerative and proliferative activity. Analysis of CD31 expression revealed structural alterations in endothelial cells and impaired angiogenesis within the microcirculatory bed. In the correction groups, partial restoration of villous architecture, re-establishment of epithelial integrity, and a decrease in inflammatory cell infiltration were observed. Although morphometric parameters improved compared with the experimental groups, they did not completely return to control values. The obtained findings suggest that the hypoxic and toxic effects of domestic gas exposure against the background of chronic alcoholism intensify degenerative and dystrophic processes in the intestinal mucosa. These alterations are primarily associated with microcirculatory disturbances, oxidative stress, and reduced cellular proliferative activity.

Conclusion. The small intestine of healthy 3-, 9-, and 15-month-old outbred rats possesses a normal morphological structure; however, certain physiological involucional changes occur with advancing age. Domestic gas poisoning against the background of chronic alcoholism induces pronounced morphological alterations in the small intestine, including villous destruction, epithelial degeneration, crypt deformation, and microcirculatory disorders. Morphometric analysis demonstrates a decrease in villus height, mucosal thickness, and proliferative activity as a consequence of the pathological process. Immunohistochemical findings, including reduced Ki-67 expression and alterations in CD31 expression, confirm impairment of regenerative processes and angiogenesis. Corrective treatment promotes reparative processes in the small intestinal tissues and leads to partial restoration of morphological and morphometric parameters.

Domestic gas intoxication in the setting of chronic alcoholism represents a significant factor disrupting the structural integrity of the intestinal mucosa, with hypoxia, microcirculatory disturbances, and decreased proliferative activity playing key roles in its pathogenesis.

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For citation: Ibodova D.F. Morphological changes in the small intestine caused by domestic gas poisoning against the background of chronic alcoholism // *Bulletin of Fundamental and Clinic Medicine*. – 2026. – № 6(26). – P. 440–442. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20675132>